

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2025, № 4 (Август)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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Interrelation of Metabolic Syndrome Components and Clinical Phenotypes of Bronchial Asthma: Evidence from the Bukhara Region

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Abstract. Bronchial asthma and metabolic syndrome are serious health problems that are growing rapidly around the world. Reversible airway obstruction with hyperresponsiveness is the main criterion for bronchial asthma, while hypertension, obesity, dyslipidemia, and type 2 diabetes mellitus are the main criteria for MS. It is estimated that a quarter of the world's population has MS and an increased cardiovascular risk compared to people without it. Diabetes is 5 times more common in people with MS. Hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia have been found to have clinically significant adverse effects on airway structure and function; performance and health status of the subjects. To date, the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in patients with bronchial asthma has not been studied enough.

Key words: bronchial asthma, metabolic syndrome, arterial hypertension, obesity, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Взаимосвязь компонентов метаболического синдрома и клинических фенотипов бронхиальной астмы: данные Бухарского региона

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Аннотация. Бронхиальная астма и метаболический синдром представляют собой серьёзные проблемы здравоохранения, распространённость которых стремительно растёт во всём мире. Обратимая обструкция дыхательных путей с гиперреактивностью является основным диагностическим критерием бронхиальной астмы, тогда как артериальная гипертензия, ожирение,

дислипидемия и сахарный диабет 2 типа — основными компонентами метаболического синдрома. По оценкам, четверть населения мира страдает метаболическим синдромом и имеет повышенный сердечно-сосудистый риск по сравнению с лицами без него. Сахарный диабет встречается примерно в 5 раз чаще у людей с метаболическим синдромом. Установлено, что гипергликемия и гиперинсулинемия оказывают клинически значимое неблагоприятное влияние на структуру и функцию дыхательных путей, физическую работоспособность и общее состояние здоровья. На сегодняшний день распространённость метаболического синдрома у пациентов с бронхиальной астмой изучена недостаточно.

Ключевые слова: бронхиальная астма, метаболический синдром, артериальная гипертензия, ожирение, дислипидемия, сахарный диабет 2 типа.

Introduction. Metabolic Syndrome (MS) is considered the “non-infectious pandemic of the 21st century” and remains one of the most pressing issues in modern medicine. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) experts, approximately 17% of women and 15% of men—about one-third of the world’s population—suffer from overweight or obesity. Moreover, in recent years, the incidence of this pathology has been particularly high among middle-aged and young people.

At the same time, the number of pathological conditions closely associated with MS continues to increase. In 1930, M.P. Konchalovsky described a combination of overweight, gout, cardiovascular diseases, and bronchial asthma (BA) under the concept of “arthritic diathesis” (or “arthritic constitution”). These observations gave rise to the hypothesis that metabolic disorders and bronchial asthma may be interrelated. Like MS, bronchial asthma remains one of the global health problems worldwide. According to estimates, the total number of patients reaches about 334 million people, and the prevalence of the disease varies from 3% to 15% in different

countries. Over the past few decades, the number of newly diagnosed asthma cases has increased more than threefold.

In 1993, in order to monitor the growing prevalence of asthma, an international expert council developed the Global Strategy for Asthma Management and Prevention (Global Initiative for Asthma, GINA), which has been revised annually ever since.

Research Objective: To study the prevalence and consequences of metabolic syndrome among patients suffering from bronchial asthma.

Materials and Methods. A cross-sectional study was conducted in 320 patients with bronchial asthma. Participants were selected from patients admitted to the pulmonology department of the regional multidisciplinary hospital. Clinical and laboratory data—including medical history, physical examination, spirometry, complete blood count, ESR, liver and kidney function tests, lipid profile (HDL cholesterol, triglycerides), and CRP levels—were analyzed. In all patients, body weight, height, BMI (kg/m^2), and waist circumference were measured.

The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) criteria were used to diagnose metabolic syndrome (MS) [4]. MS was diagnosed when at least three of the following criteria were present:

1. Waist circumference: ≥ 94 cm in men, ≥ 80 cm in women;
2. Blood pressure: systolic ≥ 130 mmHg and/or diastolic ≥ 85 mmHg, or ongoing antihypertensive therapy;
3. Fasting plasma glucose > 100 mg/dL, or ongoing treatment for hyperglycemia;
4. HDL cholesterol < 40 mg/dL in men or < 50 mg/dL in women, or receiving specific therapy for this abnormality;
5. Triglycerides ≥ 150 mg/dL, or receiving specific therapy for hypertriglyceridemia.

Results and Analysis. All biochemical and anthropometric indicators related to the diagnosis of metabolic syndrome (MS) are presented in Table 1. According to the IDF classification, MS was diagnosed in 184 (57.5%) of patients with bronchial asthma. The distribution of individual MS components among asthma patients was evaluated.

- Abdominal (central) obesity was observed in 40% of cases,
- Low HDL cholesterol — 40%,
- Elevated fasting glucose — 27.5%,
- Elevated triglycerides — 15%,
- High blood pressure — 12.5%.

Thus, in patients with bronchial asthma, the most prevalent components were low HDL cholesterol levels and abdominal-type obesity (each 40%), followed by increased fasting glucose (27.5%), while elevated triglycerides and arterial hypertension were observed less frequently (15% and 12.5%, respectively). Overall, among bronchial asthma patients, the most common MS components were increased waist circumference (40%) and low HDL cholesterol (40%), as illustrated in Figure

Table 1.

Demographic and Metabolic Characteristics of the Study Group

Clinical Parameters	Asthma (n = 320)
Age (years)	45.60 ± 11.11
Gender	
- Female	224 (70%)
- Male	96 (30%)
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	23.54 ± 3.18
Waist circumference (cm)	97.98 ± 15.55
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	133 ± 18.76

Clinical Parameters	Asthma (n = 320)
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	81 ± 10.57
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	151.05 ± 65.36
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	121.41 ± 106.59
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	49.0 ± 15.8
Fasting Plasma Glucose (mmol/L)	6.3 ± 2.1
FEV ₁ (Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 sec)	44.85 ± 17.89
FEV ₁ /FVC Ratio (%)	65.15 ± 13.02
Metabolic Syndrome (MS)	184 (57.5%)

Notes: Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation or frequency (percentage).

Abbreviations:

- BMI – Body Mass Index
- CRP – C-reactive protein
- FG – Fasting Glucose
- SBP – Systolic Blood Pressure
- DBP – Diastolic Blood Pressure
- HDL – High-Density Lipoprotein
- FEV₁ – Forced Expiratory Volume in the First Second
- MS – Metabolic Syndrome

Results (continued). Among the 136 patients with bronchial asthma without metabolic syndrome (MS criteria not met), 24 patients (7.5%) showed no signs of MS, 56 patients (17.5%) had at least one MS parameter, and another 56 patients (17.5%) had two MS parameters identified.

When comparing the asthma group without MS and the asthma group with MS, statistically significant differences were found in several parameters, including:

- Waist circumference ($P = 0.0158$),
- C-reactive protein (CRP) ($P = 0.025$),
- Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ($P = 0.0157$),
- Triglycerides ($P = 0.0264$), and
- Fasting glucose levels ($P = 0.0001$).

These data are presented in Table 2.

Correlations between MS and clinical parameters in patients with bronchial asthma are summarized in Table 3. A positive correlation was found between the presence of MS and the following parameters:

- FEV₁ ($r = 0.33$, $P < 0.03$),
- Systolic blood pressure (SBP) ($r = 0.32$, $P < 0.04$),
- Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ($r = 0.62$, $P < 0.001$), and
- Fasting glucose level (FG) ($r = 0.68$, $P < 0.001$).

These findings indicate that in asthma patients, higher blood pressure, fasting glucose, and CRP levels are significantly associated with the presence of metabolic syndrome.

Table 2.

Metabolic Syndrome Criteria in the Studied Population

Clinical Parameters	Asthma with MS	Asthma without MS	P- value
Age (years)	46.45	44.75	0. 63
Females (%)	37.5%	32.5%	0. 313
Males (%)	20%	10%	0. 053
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	23.99 ± 3.72	21.55 ± 4.33	0.

Clinical Parameters	Asthma with MS	Asthma without MS	P- value
			065
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	138.5 ± 19.40	127.5 ± 16.8	0. 06
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	87.5 ± 4.73	74.5 ± 10.87	0. 001
FVC (%)	41.95 ± 20.84	47.75 ± 14.3	0. 31
FEV ₁ /FVC (%)	63.9 ± 15.9	64.4 ± 9.56	0. 72
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	191.80 ± 70.39	110.3 ± 17.81	0. 001
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	155.4 ± 140.1	87.4 ± 35.37	0. 042
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	58.5 ± 9.5	51.7 ± 7.5	0. 47
C-reactive Protein (mg/L)	7.2 ± 1.54*	5.6 ± 2.69	0. 03

Abbreviations:

MS – Metabolic Syndrome; BMI – Body Mass Index; CRP – C-reactive Protein; FG –Fasting Glucose; SBP – Systolic Blood Pressure; DBP – Diastolic Blood Pressure; HDL – High-Density Lipoprotein; FEV₁ – Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second; FVC – Forced Vital Capacity.

Table 3.

Correlation Between Clinical Parameters and Metabolic Syndrome in Asthma Patients

Clinical Parameters		P-value
Age (years)	.05	0.74
Gender	.10	0.50
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	.26	0.10
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	.32	0.04
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	.62	0.001
FEV ₁ (Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 sec)	.33	0.03
FEV ₁ /FVC Ratio (%)	.24	0.13
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	.68	0.001
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	.24	0.13
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	.18	0.26
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	.08	0.59

Clinical Parameters		P-value
C-reactive Protein (mg/L)	.01	0.93

Conclusion. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome (MS) among patients with bronchial asthma (BA) was found to be high in our study. The findings indicate the importance of developing comprehensive strategies aimed at the prevention and management of comorbidities in patients with existing MS.

Timely identification of risk factors for metabolic syndrome can play a crucial role in preventing complications and improving the quality of life in patients suffering from bronchial asthma.

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